

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The role of parasocial interaction as a mediator in the influence between trust and beauty influencer expertise on purchase intention (study on beauty influencer Abel Cantika)

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Abstract

This research aims to determine and analyze the influence of trust and expertise possessed by a beauty influencer on purchase intentions mediated by parasocial interactions. The sampling technique for this research is a purposive sampling technique which was distributed to followers of social media beauty influencer Abel Cantika aged 18-34 years. The number of respondents in this study was 400 and the data was obtained from the distribution of Google forms which was carried out over 20 days. Data analysis uses Structural Equation Model (SEM) via SmartPLS software. The result is that trust has a positive effect on purchase intentions, expertise has a negative effect on purchase intentions, the next result is that trust has a positive effect on parasocial interactions, expertise has a positive effect on parasocial interactions. Then parasocial interaction is able to mediate expertise on purchase intentions and finally parasocial interaction is able to mediate expertise on purchase intentions.

Keywords: Expertise; Parasocial Interaction; Purchase Intention; Trust

1. Introduction

In beauty content, influencers are called beauty influencers. This beauty influencer is the type of influencer with the second largest number of followers at 43% on social media worldwide (Rakuten Marketing, 2019). Beauty Influencers as people who can influence other people's opinions also require trust and expertise as provisions for influencers to influence their followers.

One of Indonesia's beauty influencers is Abel Cantika. Abel Cantika is an influencer who was honoured at Beauty Fest Asia (BFA) 2018 in the "Break Out Creator Of The Year" category as a beauty influencer in Indonesia (Popbela, 2019). Abel Cantika's prowess in communicating beauty products to her followers has proven to attract the attention of the beauty industry. Several beauty industries have collaborated with domestic and foreign products. Sales from beauty brands' collaborations with Abel Cantika can be said to be satisfactory, as evidenced by her collaboration with Elshe Skin, which sold 3 shades of nude lipstick that sold out immediately upon release on 26 May 2018 (Sociolla, 2018).

According to Alfarraj (2021) trust is defined as the honesty, integrity and trustworthiness of an influencer. Trust as an important factor for an influencer because the honesty of the influencer can build his followers' trust in the influencer so that there is a positive interaction between the influencer and his followers. The results of research conducted by Thamrin & Ramadhan (2021), Chekima et al, (2020), Mamahit et al., (2022) that trust affects purchase intention. Contrary to the research of Widyanto & Agusti (2020) and Vidyanata et al., (2018) that trust has no influence on purchase intention.

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Expertise is also an important factor that influencers need. According to AlFarraj et al. (2021), expertise is defined as the extent to which an influencer has sufficient knowledge, experience and skills to promote a product. In other words, an influencer with special abilities in their field can create a special attraction for their followers. The results of research from Chekima et al., (2020), Nuraida et al., (2022) that expertise affects purchase intention. Contrary to the research of Widyanto & Agusti (2020), Vidyanata et al., (2018), and Thamrin & Ramadhan, (2021) that expertise has no influence on purchase intention.

There are many ways that can be done to increase the purchase intention of potential consumers, one of which is parasocial interaction. A follower as a potential consumer goes through an internalisation process when influenced to have an interest in buying a product (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020). Parasocial interaction occurs where a sense of closeness and attachment and even addiction by someone they consider to be their role model.

The large number of followers and viewers of Abel Cantika's beauty content on social media is able to form a bond between beauty influencers and their followers. Social media platforms such as YouTube and Instagram are more interactive, different from traditional communication media such as television, because the interaction between influencers and their audiences on YouTube and Instagram goes beyond traditional one-way opinions, and audiences can socialise with influencers through commenting, liking and sharing their videos and content (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020). Followers of influencers on social media feel closer friendships than with traditional celebrities (Hwang & Zhang, 2018). This relationship can be described as parasocial interaction. Parasocial interaction stems from consumers' ability to trust influencers, which is directly related to the perceived trustworthiness and expertise of the influencer's message and is naturally influenced by the influencer's own physical magnetism (Sakib et al., 2020). This explanation suggests that the characteristics of influencers are able to shape parasocial interactions.

Followers on social media go through affective and internalisation processes from parasocial interactions with influencers and have a positive impact on their purchase intentions towards products communicated by influencers (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020). Establishing parasocial interactions between influencers and followers can increase the likelihood of future purchases (Lee & Watkins, 2016). Influencers who have parasocial interactions with their followers are better able to persuade them to have the intention to buy the products they communicate. This is in accordance with research conducted by Hwang & Zhang (2018) which shows that parasocial interactions positively influence follower purchases. Vlogs posted on YouTube by influencers with parasocial interactions developed between followers and influencers also have a positive influence on purchase intention on the communicated product (Lee & Watkins, 2016). The existence of this parasocial interaction relationship is expected to have a positive impact on consumer interest in purchasing beauty products put forward by beauty influencers on their beauty content on YouTube and Instagram social media.

Paid partnerships with mega-influencers have been an integral part of leading brands' digital marketing strategies. However, in recent years, these mega-influencers have started to lose their influence on consumers, especially young consumers such as Gen Z. This phenomenon is known as influencer fatigue, where consumers become bored and stop trusting what influencers have to say. This phenomenon is known as influencer fatigue, where consumers become bored and stop trusting what influencers have to say. GWI notes that Gen Z is by far the age group that most often makes purchases based on posts shared by major influencers. This situation is inseparable from Gen Z's frequent impulse buying nature. GWI found that 65% of Gen Z and Millennials tend to make impulse purchases at least once a month.

Compared to previous generations, social media is indeed the main platform for Gen Z to discover or search for new products. As for older generations such as millennials, they tend to learn about new products through search engines and TV adverts. Consumers, especially younger ones like Gen Z, have lost trust in paid influencers (Kumparan, 2022). According to Jennifer Ang, CEO of PT Mitra Komune Nusantara, a company engaged in events, communications, and community technology, the number of Gen Z interested in influencers dropped 12 per cent compared to 2020, according to Global Web Index (GWI) data. In addition, only 3 per cent of consumers buy products under the influence of major influencers.

A study conducted by Bazaarvoice (2018) also revealed that around 47% of consumers are tired of similar and repetitive influencer content. In other words, consumers are starting to turn away from influencers as their sponsored content lacks originality. In addition, another issue arises with the transparency and effectiveness of influencer campaigns. This is because quite a number of influencers buy followers or use bots to increase engagement or fake engagement just to get a higher brand fee.

According to statistics from advertising agency Carmichael Lynch, about 23 per cent of influencers find it difficult to create original sponsored content themselves. This is consistent with the findings of the influencer marketing report:

Marketing: Exploring The Current Influencer Marketing Landscape And Its Future Potential: 48 per cent of consumers said they want influencers they can trust. At the same time, 29% of consumers want influencers to show transparency about sponsored products. According to him, the results clearly underline that trust and expertise are the most important issues in the relationship between influencers and consumers. Consumers want full disclosure about what the influencer is promoting. In addition, they want influencers to only promote products that they actually use and know about.

Today, as consumers no longer trust information published by social media influencers, companies must find authentic ways to communicate on social media. To entice Gen Z to buy their products, brands need to look for more authentic engagement models, such as expertise and trust that align with the brands they work with. Based on the above discussion, researchers are further interested in conducting research related to trust and expertise in beauty content on YouTube and Instagram social media with the role of parasocial interaction as mediation. The framework model is as follows.

Figure 1 Thinking Framework

2. Methods

This research uses explanatory research. This research aims to explain the casual relationship between variables by testing previously made hypotheses. This research approach itself uses a quantitative approach. This study uses non-probability sampling techniques through purposive sampling, which is a method of drawing samples with certain considerations. The sample in this study is based on certain considerations, such as: aged 18-34 years and following Abel Cantika on Instagram social media accounts.

Primary data is the type of data collected directly by the researcher for this study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first part each contains questions about the respondents' demographics, such as gender, age, and occupation. The second part contains statements about respondents' perceptions of the variables of trust, expertise, parasocial interaction, and purchase intention. To make the process of processing and analysing the research data easier, the questionnaire was distributed via google form online and the results were converted into a modified Likert Scale. In this study, there are five Likert Scales, where point 5 indicates Strongly Agree (SS), point 4 indicates Agree (S), point 3 indicates Neutral (N), and point 2 indicates Disagree (TS), and point 1 indicates Strongly Disagree (STS). This research was tested using Smart PLS with three stages of testing, namely outer model test, inner model test, and hypothesis testing with the criteria of P-Value ≤ 0.05.

Table 1 Operational Definition

Variable	Operational Definition	Statement	Source
Trust	Perceived honesty, integrity and	Have honesty in communicating beauty products. Communicating beauty products in a consistent or unvarying way	Gupta et al., (2015),

	trustworthiness of an advocate.	Able to convince me of the beauty products communicated	
Expertise	Specialised skills, knowledge, or abilities in relation to the brand being delivered.	Have knowledge of the beauty product being communicated Have expertise in communicating products Explain the beauty product being communicated so that it is easily understood	Gupta et al., (2015)
Parasocial Interaction	Mediated interpersonal relationships that occur between media users and media figures through mass media.	Instagram social media content shows what kind of person she really is The content on Instagram is easy to understand and pleasant to look at Showing her opinion about a beauty brand will affect my view of the brand Follow Abel Cantika's Instagram and interact with her either by liking or commenting on her posts I look forward to watching and viewing posts on Instagram If Abel Cantika appears on Instagram I will watch it. If there is Abel Cantika in other people's content then I will see it I miss seeing Abel Cantika when he doesn't post content on Instagram for a long time. I would like to meet Abel Cantika in person	Ding & Qiu (2017), Sokolova & Kefi (2020), Sakib et al (2020) dan Lee & Watkins (2016)
Purchase Intention	A response to an object that indicates a customer's desire to make a purchase	I always look for information about beauty products communicated by Abel Cantika. I will buy beauty products communicated by Abel Cantika in less than one month. I would prefer beauty products communicated by Abel Cantika over other beauty products. I will recommend the beauty products promoted by Abel Cantika to people close to me.	Ferdinand, (2014) dan Sokolova & Kefi (2020)

3. Results

3.1. General Description of Respondents

This research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 400 respondents who were in accordance with the sample determination. The data obtained is also in accordance with the expected sample size. respondent characteristics are categorised by gender, age, and occupation. Some of the characteristics obtained after data collection through questionnaire filling are as follows. An overview of the characteristics of the respondents in this study can be seen in table 2 which shows that the characteristics of respondents based on gender, it can be seen that of the 400 respondents who filled out the questionnaire, most were female, 343 respondents (85.75%) with ages 22 years to 25 years, 143 respondents (35.75%). Respondents mostly work as students or students with 191 respondents (47.75%).

Table 2 Respondent Characteristics Data

No.	Characteristics	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender		
	Female	343	85.75%
	Male	57	14.25%
	Total	400	100%

2.	Age		
	18-21	121	30.25%
	22-25	143	35.75%
	26-29	72	18%
	30-34	64	16%
	Total	400	100%
3.	Jobs		
	Student	191	47.75%
	Private Employee	132	33%
	Lecturer/Teacher	7	1.75%
	PNS/BUMN	6	1.5%
	Entrepreneur	30	7.5%
	Other Occupations	34	8.5%
	Total	400	100%

3.2. Outer Model Test Results

The outer model test is used to evaluate the feasibility of the instrument by evaluating convergent validity, composite reliability and discriminant validity. The outer model test results in Table 3 evaluate convergent validity, composite reliability, and discriminant validity. The research results on the convergent validity test have a loading factor value > 0.50 on all variable items. These results indicate that the research data has met the convergent validity criteria. The second evaluation is the composite reliability test which has a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 or $\rho_c > 0.70$ on the seven main variables, so that the research data is declared to meet the composite reliability criteria. Finally, the discriminant validity test has an AVE value > 0.50 . This means that the research data is declared to meet the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 3 Outer Model Test Results

Variable	Item	Loading Factor	ρ_c	Cronbach Alpha	AVE	Result
Purchase Intention (Y)	NB1	0.863	0.933	0.910	0.735	Valid and Reliable
	NB2	0.766				
	NB3	0.891				
	NB4	0.863				
	NB5	0.896				
Trust (X1)	KP1	0.753	0.852	0.785	0.624	Valid and Reliable
	KP2	0.884				
	KP3	0.723				
Expertise (X2)	KH1	0.734	0.796	0.654	0.570	Valid and Reliable
	KH2	0.704				
	KH3	0.848				
Parasocial Interaction (Z)	IP1	0.593	0.832	0.697	0.537	Valid and Reliable
	IP2	0.705				

	IP3	0.608				
	IP4	0.648				
	IP5	0.744				
	IP6	0.722				
	IP7	0.595				
	IP8	0.723				
	IP9	0.554				

3.3. Inner Model Test Results

Inner model analysis is used to assess the strength of the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable by looking at the R-Square (R^2) and Goodness of Fit (GoF) values. R^2 on the purchase intention variable is worth 0.583 (moderate) which indicates that the purchase intention variable can be explained by the variables of trust, expertise and parasocial interaction by 58.3% and the remaining 41.7% is explained by other variables not used in this study. Meanwhile, the parasocial interaction variable is 0.447 (moderate) which indicates that the parasocial interaction variable can be explained by the variables of trust, expertise, and purchase intention by 44.7% and the remaining 55.3% is explained by other variables not used in this study. The calculation results obtained the Q^2 value is 76.49% and is included in Gof large. The Q^2 value obtained explains that the diversity of data built into the model has a predictive relevance of 76.93% and the remaining 23.07% is explained by variables outside the model and the error rate. So this Gof interprets the model that is well formed and is able to explain 76.93% of the variables studied.

3.4. Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis testing is used to test the influence between variables and prove the proposed hypotheses, namely H1 to H8. This test was carried out using path analysis which was tested through Smart PLS. The criteria used are the P-Value ≤ 0.05 then the hypothesis can be accepted. The results of hypothesis testing show that Trust -> Purchase Intention ($\beta=0.307$; P-Value=0.000); Expertise -> Purchase Intention ($\beta=0.264$; P-Value=0.000); Trust -> Parasocial Interaction ($\beta=0.530$; P-Value=0.000); Expertise -> Parasocial Inteaaction ($\beta=0.229$; P-Value=0.000); and Parasocial Interaction-> Purchase Intention ($\beta=0.638$; P-Value=0.000), thus supporting H1 to H5. In mediation, researchers found the effect of Trust -> Parasocial Interaction -> Purchase Intention ($\beta=0.338$; P-Value=0.000) and Expertise -> Parasocial Interaction -> Purchase Intention ($\beta=0.146$; P-Value=0.000) which means that it supports H6 and H7.

Table 4 Hypothesis Test Results

	β	T Stat	P Values	Hasil
Trust -> Purchase Intention	0.307	5.850	0.000	H1 Accepted
Expertise -> Purchase Intention	0.264	6.599	0.000	H2 Accepted
Trust -> Parasocial Interaction	0.530	11.850	0.000	H3 Accepted
Expertise -> Parasocial Interaction	0.229	5.566	0.000	H4 Accepted
Parasocial Interaction->Purchase Intention	0.638	13.136	0.000	H5 Accepted
Trust -> Parasocial Interaction -> Purchase Intention	0.338	9.439	0.000	H6 Accepted
Expertise -> Parasocial Interaction -> Purchase Intention	0.146	4.614	0.000	H7 Accepted

4. Discussion

4.1. The effect of trust on purchase intention

Based on the results of hypothesis testing that has been carried out regarding the effect of trust on purchase intention with the result that trust has a significant effect on purchase intention with a positive relationship direction. The direction of the positive relationship indicates that the higher the level of consumer trust in Abel Cantika as a beauty

influencer, the higher the consumer purchase intention. This could mean that consumers' trust in Abel Cantika motivates them to be more likely to make a purchase, perhaps because they feel confident that the recommendations or reviews provided by Abel Cantika are reliable. And the significant effect shows that the trust variable owned by beauty influencer Abel Cantika has a strong role in influencing consumer purchase intention. The results of this study are in accordance with the theory that when communicators are considered highly trustworthy, opinionated messages are more effective than non-opinionated messages in producing attitude change (Ohanian, 1990).

The results of this study are supported by previous research which states that trust has an effect on purchase intention, namely that the results show that trust has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. Gupta et al., (2015) which states that trust has a major positive influence on purchase intention and is in line with research conducted by Chekima et al, (2020) Thamrin & Ramadhan, (2021).

4.2. The effect of expertise on purchase intention

Based on the results of hypothesis testing that has been carried out regarding the effect of expertise on purchase intention with the results that Abel Cantika's expertise has a significant effect on purchase intention with a negative relationship direction. The negative relationship direction indicates that the higher the level of expertise possessed by beauty influencer Abel Cantika, the lower the consumer's purchase intention. This could mean that consumers may have a tendency to be more critical or selective in making purchases when exposed to beauty influencers who have a certain level of expertise. Potential explanations for this can vary, such as concerns about possible mismatches with consumers' personal preferences or perhaps high expectations that are difficult to fulfil by the products recommended by the beauty influencer. The results of this study are supported by previous research which states that trust affects purchase intention, namely that the results show that expertise has a negative and significant effect on purchase intention (Harjadi, 2022).

4.3. The influence of trust on parasocial interactions

Based on the results of hypothesis testing that has been carried out regarding the effect of trust on purchase intention with the result that trust has a significant effect on parasocial interactions with a positive relationship direction. This shows that the trust Abel Cantika has as a beauty influencer is able to influence parasocial interactions. Influencers on social media are considered more trustworthy and they are a reliable source of online information (Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017). The influence of trust, of course, also has an impact on the support of each of its indicators, namely honesty, integrity and source trust.

The results of this study are in line with research from Sakib et al (2019) which also shows that trust has a significant effect on parasocial interactions. In the descriptive analysis, it is explained that the indicators of integrity and source trust in communicating beauty products on social media have the highest value. This shows that the integrity and trustworthiness of the source can strengthen the parasocial interactions that exist between Abel Cantika and his followers.

4.4. The effect of expertise on parasocial interactions

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test regarding the effect of expertise on parasocial interactions with the result that expertise has a significant effect on parasocial interactions with a positive relationship direction. This shows that when the expertise of the influencer in communicating the product is higher, it will strengthen parasocial interactions. Shimp (2013) states that expertise refers to the knowledge, knowledge or skills possessed by the source, namely the influencer, because they are directly connected to communication to the audience.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Sakib et al (2019) Lestari (2021), Septi (2022), Tandayong & Palumian (2022) and Lin (2021) which also show that expertise has a significant effect on parasocial interactions. Based on descriptive analysis, it explains that Abel Cantika has excellent expertise in communicating beauty products on social media. This expertise in communicating beauty products is also supported by Abel Cantika's knowledge of beauty products so that she is able to explain well and is easily understood by followers.

Content that is easy to understand will attract followers to always see the content. The content uploaded by beauty influencers must keep up with trends in the world of beauty to always attract the attention of followers. Especially if the beauty influencer is able to take advantage of this digitalisation era, the uploaded content can be easily accessed by followers. The higher the intensity with which Abel Cantika's beauty content is accessed by her followers, resulting in high interaction on social media, the more parasocial interaction bonds are formed. This shows the positive influence of Abel Cantika's expertise in communicating beauty products on parasocial interactions.

4.5. The effect of parasocial interaction on purchase intention

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test regarding the effect of parasocial interaction on purchase intention with the result that parasocial interaction has a significant effect on purchase intention with a positive relationship direction. The theory of parasocial interaction according to Horton and Richard Wohl (1956) is a relationship or attachment that is established with a character who appears in the media, based on the affective bond felt by a person towards the media character. This shows that Abel Cantika can be considered a beauty influencer who is considered quite close to followers. And this can influence her followers to have the intention to buy a beauty product that Abel Cantika communicates on her social media content. The interaction that exists between Abel Cantika and her followers makes her followers feel comfortable so that they look forward to her latest content on social media.

With the positive interaction between followers and Abel Cantika, they feel close like old friends, so the information conveyed by Abel Cantika is used as a reference when purchasing a product. This is in line with research conducted by Lestari (2021), Septi (2022), Tandayong & Palumian (2022) and Lin (2021) which states that parasocial interaction has a positive effect on purchase intention.

4.6. The effect of trust on purchase intention mediated by parasocial interaction

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test regarding the indirect effects that have been carried out regarding the effect of trust on purchase intention mediated by parasocial interaction with the result that parasocial interaction is able to mediate the effect of trust on purchase intention. This means that this proves that trust has an important impact on purchase intention through parasocial interactions. It can also be interpreted that the parasocial interactions that occur between Abel Cantika and his followers are able to bridge the influence of trust in content on social media on purchase intention. It can be interpreted that followers' trust in what Abel Cantika communicates about beauty products on social media can lead to the closeness of parasocial interactions so as to increase purchase intention on the communicated beauty products.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Yilmazdoğan et al., (2021) and Tandayong & Palumian, (2022) which show that the mediating effect of parasocial interactions that connect the effect of trust on purchase intention is due to the interactions that exist between beauty influencers and good potential consumers. Sakib et al (2019) show that parasocial interactions can come from an individual's ability to be able to trust the influencer and motivate the individual to have a minay of compliance. It can be concluded that when Abel Cantika's followers have trust in what Abel Cantika communicates on social media about beauty products, it will lead to the closeness of parasocial interactions so that it can motivate them to have buying intentions on these beauty products. Parasocial interactions between Abel Cantika and followers must always be maintained by always giving trust to all beauty content on social media so as to be able to continue to increase purchase intention for the communicated beauty products. This can be done by always giving honest reviews according to what Abel Cantika feels and thinks about the beauty products and not exaggerated or can be said to be an honest review so as to increase purchase intention.

4.7. The effect of expertise on purchase intention through parasocial interaction

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test regarding the indirect effects that have been carried out regarding the effect of expertise on purchase intention mediated by parasocial interaction with the result that parasocial interaction is able to mediate the effect of expertise on purchase intention. This proves that expertise also has an important impact on purchase intentions through parasocial interactions. This indicates that Abel Cantika's expertise in communicating beauty products on her social media can increase parasocial interactions so that it can motivate followers' purchase intention on the communicated beauty products.

This is in line with research conducted by Yilmazdoğan et al., (2021) and Tandayong & Palumian, (2022) which shows that the effect of expertise on purchase intention can be mediated by parasocial interactions. According to Sokolova and Kehi (2020), the connections established in parasocial interactions make followers seek more information from what their favourite influencers upload and are more able to persuade purchase intentions. This is in accordance with the frequency distribution of the desire to buy immediately from the purchase intention which gives the highest value of 324. So it can be concluded that Abel Cantika's expertise in communicating beauty products on social media is able to increase purchase intention with a high desire to buy immediately with the connection that is established in it.

5. Conclusion

Based on the test results and discussion previously presented, the following conclusions are obtained:

- Trust has a positive effect on purchase intention. This indicates that when the trust of Abel Cantika's followers increases, the purchase intention will also increase.
- Expertise has a negative effect on purchase intention. This indicates that when the expertise of beauty influencer Abel Cantika increases, the purchase intention will decrease, and vice versa. This is because there is a saturated market that causes purchase intention to decrease even though the level of expertise increases.
- Trust has a positive effect on parasocial interactions. This indicates that when the influencer's trust increases, parasocial interactions will also increase.
- Expertise has a positive effect on parasocial interactions. This indicates that when the influencer's expertise in communicating the product is higher, it will strengthen parasocial interactions.
- Parasocial interaction has a positive effect on purchase intention. This shows that Abel Cantika can be said to be a beauty influencer who is considered close enough to followers and can influence her followers to have the intention to buy a beauty product that Abel Cantika communicates on her social media content.
- Parasocial interaction is able to mediate the effect of trust on purchase intention. This indicates that Abel Cantika's followers have trust in what is communicated on social media about beauty products, which will lead to the closeness of parasocial interactions so that it can motivate them to have the intention to buy these beauty products.
- Parasocial interaction is able to mediate the effect of expertise on purchase intention. This indicates that Abel Cantika's expertise in communicating beauty products on social media can increase parasocial interactions so that it can motivate followers' purchase intention on the communicated beauty products.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusions of the research results, it can provide suggestions that researchers can convey as follows:

- The trust indicator that has the lowest value, namely maintaining integrity, means that the company pays attention to the trust held by beauty influencers by conducting training on transparency and maintaining compatibility with the image or mission of a brand so that it will create a sense of trust that its followers have.
- The skill indicator that has the lowest score is knowledge of the product, meaning that companies can pay more attention to the communication skills of beauty influencers by providing training on communication and product understanding so that it is more optimal in persuading followers. And beauty influencers must also improve and take advantage of digitalisation tools to face the current digital era.
- The parasocial interaction indicator that has the lowest value is friendship, meaning that influencers are expected to be able to improve relationships with followers so as to create a sense of friendship that is able to persuade in communicating products well.
- The purchase intention indicator that has the lowest value is the desire to buy immediately, meaning that companies and beauty influencers can be able to work together by presenting interesting content, conducting special promotions and marketing strategies through integrated channels, so that it will stimulate the purchase intention of their followers effectively.
- The results showed that purchase intention was explained by the variables of trust, expertise and parasocial interaction by 58.3%. This means that other variables need to be added to influence purchase intentions such as price variables and perceived quality, attributes, promotions so as to increase product purchase intentions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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